

Training Needs Assessment of Coastal Residents of Orani: Basis for Gender-Based Extension Program

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the training needs assessment of the coastal residents in the (4) four Barangay of Orani, Bataan. The research design employed in this study was the descriptive method. The researcher used a random sampling technique. The respondents of the study were the (100) one hundred coastal residents in Orani, Bataan. The data in this study were obtained using the researcher-made questionnaire intended to determine the profile and training needs of the coastal residents. Frequency, percentage, and weighted mean were the statistical tools used to determine the problems proposed. The findings revealed that the respondents wanted to have a skills and livelihood training program in their respective barangay. The majority of the training needs assessment in terms of skills and livelihood training program wished to have training on automotive technology, food processing, basic cookery, Welding, and candle making respectively. The study also revealed that the coastal residents of the selected barangay in Orani, Bataan agreed to support the programs to be conducted by the institution. It was concluded that the coastal residents need the following training based on the result and it was recommended that the institution find ways to develop and implement a viable gender-based Extension Program for the coastal residents, the personnel or extensionists should also work hand in hand in improving the service of delivery of extension services to target clientele, proper monitoring on the financial practices utilized in the project should be done periodically. An intensive monitoring and assessment should be made to meet the standards set by the government with regards to extension services operation reared the welfare of its client.

Keywords: training needs assessment, gender-based extension program, skills and livelihood training

Introduction

According to Bataan Coastal Care Foundation, Inc. (2006), about 1 million coastal residents and their families – about 5 percent of the nation’s labor force – earn a living directly from fisheries of the total number of individuals who rely on fish for their livelihood, 69 percent are municipal fisherfolk, 25 percent are engaged in aquaculture, and the remaining 6 percent are involved in commercial fishing.

In many coastal communities, the majority of households depend directly on fish and other coastal resources for their livelihood. Municipal fisherfolks are among the poorest in Philippine society, with an annual average household income of Php70,000, which is about half the nation's average of Php 144,000. Other studies report even lower levels of income among fisherfolk.

Among fishing families, household sizes are generally larger than the national average, and a greater proportion of their income is spent on food. The level of education of fisherfolk household heads is lower than average. In terms of access to basic services, fisherfolk households have lower rates of access. Within the coastal zone, near-shore fisheries are the most heavily exploited. An increasing number of smaller fisher families compete with each other, as well as with commercial fishermen for fishery resources that have experienced serious declines in productivity in the last 10 to 15 years.

The national administration has already initiated livelihood programs and projects to address the issue of poverty and uplift the economic status of the Philippines. Different government agencies were required to anchor their community programs to this national thrust of the government. Livelihood programs are seen to be answers to ease the concurring incidence of poverty among families in different regions especially in coastal areas. Unfortunately, some programs of the government do not directly address the needs of the community making these programs a loss. As such, parts of this venture are Higher Education Institutions (HEI’s) in the Philippines whether private or public colleges or universities that are obliged to conduct community extension programs under CHED Memorandum Order No.28 Series of 2006. This call requires all the institutions to include extensions in their school agenda. Bataan Peninsula State University, as one of the State Universities in Region III, fulfils its fourfold functions- instruction, research, extension, and production as a commitment to service to its community. The institution aside from accomplishing its main function is dedicated to creating livelihood programs embodying social responsibility.

This study is an assessment of the coastal residents of Orani to answer the training needs that are of interest and capable of. This study also looked into the available resources within the barangays and utilized them as a means of livelihood. The researchers would be of utmost willingness to recommend to extension educators and implementers a concrete and sustainable project from the results of the assessment to improve the socio-economic capacity of the residents and the standard of living of the local community.

Methods

The descriptive method was used in the study. Ardales (2008) also contends that descriptive research is appropriate for studies that aim to find out what prevails in the present; conditions or relationships held by opinion and beliefs, processes and effects, and developing trends. This type of research describes the data and characteristics of what is being studied. The researchers aimed to identify the training needs of coastal residents in Orani and analyze if these needs will be the basis for implementing a sustainable livelihood extension program for the community. As such, the descriptive method will be most suited for the study to further describe what exists within the barangay. A standard institutional survey questionnaire was used in the gathering of data.

The questionnaire has four main parts. The first part is about the profile of the coastal residents. The second part involves the socio-economic profile of the respondents. The third part includes the identification of all the training needs of the respondents. The fourth was a study on the extent of support given by the residents to community extension programs and services and the last part is the proposal of a livelihood training program and determine the costs and benefits of training.

The respondents of the study are the coastal residents of Orani, Bataan ages 25 to 64 years old only and not holding any position in the LGU. The researcher will use Sloven's formula to get the sample size and random sampling. The researchers used random sampling. The participants in this study were randomly selected. In particular, twenty-five (25) coastal residents in Pantalan Luma, twenty-five (25) in Pantalan Bago, twenty-five (25) Palihan, and twenty-five (25) coastal residents in Tapulao. Frequency counts, percentages, and weighted mean values will be used for the statistical computation of the gathered data. The data will then be gathered, analyzed, and interpreted to arrive at definite findings.

Results and Discussion

The presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the study are categorized based on the methods used and arranged based on the specific questions raised beforehand to arrive at and establish consistency and better comprehension. The data gathered is represented in tabular and textual form with the aid of statistical treatment for analysis and interpretation.

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Age	F	%
25 - 30 years old	6	6
31 - 35 years old	17	17
36 - 40 years old	16	16
41 - 45 years old	33	33
50 and above	28	28
Total	100	100

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of age. The table implies that the majority of the respondents were aged 41 – 45 years old with 33 percent and 25 – 30 years old got the lowest percentage of 6%. In that matter, it can be concluded that the respondents are in their middle adulthood where expanding personal and social involvement and responsibility are present.

Table 2. Profile of the Respondents in terms of Sex

Sex	F	%
Male	50	50
Female	50	50
Total	100	100

Table 2 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of sex. There is an equal percentage of respondents of both males and females having a percentage of 50% for each sex. Hence, it can be concluded that there is an equal representation of both women and men in this study since there is an equal number of respondents on both women and men participants. Hunt (2004), stated that equal representation of women and men in the study can be used to ensure that men and women are not disadvantaged by development activities, to enhance the sustainability and effectiveness of activities, or to identify priority areas for action to promote equality between women and men.

Table 3. Profile of the respondents in terms of Years of Stay in the Barangay

Years of Stay in Barangay	F	%
0 – 5 years	23	23
6 – 10 years	29	29
11 – 15 years	6	6
15 years and above	7	7
Since birth	35	35
Total	100	100

Table 3 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of years of stay in the barangay. It shows that 35% of the families were in that particular barangay since birth. It is followed by those who stay in the barangay for 6 – 10 years with 29% and with the lowest percentage of 11 – 15 years of stay in the barangay.

Table 4. Profile of the Respondents in terms of Members of the Family

Members of the Family	F	%
1 - 3	63	63
4 - 6	26	26
7 - 9	9	9
10 and above	2	2
Total	100	100
Number of Children	F	Mean
0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5,6	100	1.20
Number of Members of the Family with job	F	Mean
0, 1, 2, 3, 4	100	1.24
Number of Members of the Family ages 17 and below	F	Mean
0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5	100	0.73
Number of Members of the Family ages 65 and above	F	Mean
0, 1, 2, 3, 4	100	0.29
Do you have Members of the Family with a disability?	F	%
Yes	7	7
No	93	93
Total	100	100

Furthermore, Table 4 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of the members of the family. Specifically, the members of the family were also classified or identified in terms of the number of children, number of members of the family with jobs, number of members of the family ages 17 and below, number of members of the family ages 65 and above, and if the respondents have members with disabilities.

In terms of members of the family, 1 – 3 members got the highest percentage of 63%. It was followed by 4 – 6 members with 26% and 10 members and above got the lowest percentage of 2%.

In terms of several children, the overall mean of 1.20 indicates that in totality there is only one (1) child per family. The weighted mean of 1.24, indicates that there is at least one (1) member per family has a job. There is also one (1) member of the family ages 17 and below with a 0.73 weighted mean. Only a few or considered no members ages 65 and above have 0.29 as the mean. Finally, 93% of the respondents declared that they don't have members with disability, and 7% of them have members with disability. Among the disabilities stated by the respondents are as follows: eye disorder, mental illness, and other sickness.

Table 5. Profile of the Respondents in terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	F	%
Elementary Undergraduate	25	25
Elementary Graduate	37	37
High School Undergraduate	13	13
High School Graduate	17	17
College Graduate	6	6
Vocational Graduate	2	2
Total	100	100

Table 5 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of their educational attainment. Thirty-seven percent of the respondents were elementary graduates. It also shows that there is a lower percentage of college and vocational graduates having 2% and 6% respectively. Truly, education is vital for a highly skilled and productive labor force. This study seeks to quantify the relationships between additional educational attainment and employment opportunities, wage rates, and aggregate economic growth. Holtz-Eakin and Lee (2019) explained that increasing education attainment would have powerful positive effects on the economy. Specifically, as individuals attain greater education, their probability of employment rises; and greater education, including certification for those without a high school or college degree, also increases workers' ability to command higher wages. Thus, post-secondary educational attainment of all types would not just increase employment opportunities and wages in the labor market, but would also spur widespread and stronger economic growth.

Table 6. Socio-economic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Monthly Income

Monthly Income	F	%
Php5,000.00 and below	26	26
Php10,000.00 – Php15,999.00	20	20
Php16,000.00 – Php19,999.00	51	51
Php20,000.00 – Php24,999.00	2	2
Php25,000.00 – Php29,999.00	1	1
Php30,000.00 and above	0	0
Total	100	100

Table 6 indicates the socio-economic profile of the respondents in terms of monthly income. It shows that the majority of the coastal residents have Php16,000.00 to Php19,999.00 monthly income with 51%. None of the residents acquire Php30,000.00 and above as a monthly income and 1% have Php25,000.00 to Php29,999.00 as income. According to The Philippines Today (2021), a Filipino family of five's economic standing is based on their monthly income. Data was presented to the Senate finance committee by the Philippine

Institute for Development Studies (PIDS) namely: low income but not poor with Php 10,957 to Php 21,914; lower middle with Php 21,914 to Php 43,828; middle class with Php 43,828 to Php 76,669; upper middle with Php 76,669 to Php 131,484; upper but not rich with Php 131,484 to Php 219,140; and rich with Php 219,140. Hence, it can be concluded that the coastal residents of Orani belong to low-income but not poor residents.

Table 7. Socio-economic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Monthly Expenses

Monthly Expenses	F	%
Php5,000.00 and below	35	35
Php10,000.00 – Php15,999.00	12	12
Php16,000.00 – Php19,999.00	0	0
Php20,000.00 – Php24,999.00	52	52
Php25,000.00 – Php29,999.00	0	0
Php30,000.00 and above	0	0
Total	100	100

Table 7 presents the socio-economic profile of the respondents in terms of monthly expenses. It shows that the majority of the coastal residents have Php20,000.00 to Php24,999.00 monthly expenses with 52%. It was then followed by Php5,000.00 and below with 35%. It can also be noticed that the monthly expenses of the residents were greater than their monthly income. Commission on Population and Development states that the average Filipino family spends nearly half of its resources per month on food. The Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) reported that at the end of the second quarter of 2018, food expenditure stood at 41.5 percent of total household expenditure. In the Philippines, more than half of family members are identified as dependents, based on the Philippine Statistics Authority's (PSA) July 2018 overall dependency ratio of 57.7 percent. This means that the total family income is mostly spent on food and less spending is made on clothing and other basic service necessities such as housing, electricity, water, and other social services such as health and education.

Therefore, families with the highest poverty incidence such as those in the fishing and agriculture sectors are hardest hit as the high inflation rate remains unabated, making the daily survival of poor Filipino families hard to address, more so with increasing family size.

Table 8. Socio-economic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Source of Income

Source of Income	F	%
Crop farming and gardening such as growing palay, corn, roots, vegetables, fruits, nuts, ornamental plants, etc.	1	1
Livestock and poultry raising such as raising of carabaos, cattle, hogs, horses, chickens, ducks, etc., and the production of fresh milk, eggs, etc.	2	2
Fishing activities such as capture of fish; gathering of fry, shells, seaweeds, etc.; culturing fish, oysters, mussels, etc.	27	27
Forestry and hunting activities such as tree planting (falcata, gmelina, rubber trees, etc.), firewood gathering, small-scale logging, charcoal making, gathering of forestry products (cogon, nipa, rattan, bamboo, resin, gum, etc.) or hunting of wild animals/birds, etc.	0	0
Wholesale and retail trade including market vending, sidewalk vending, peddling, etc.	6	6
Manufacturing activities such as mat weaving, tailoring, dressmaking, bagoong making, fish drying, etc.	3	3
Community, social, and personal services such as medical and dental practice, practice of trade, operation of schools, restaurants and hotels, etc.	3	3
Transportation, storage, and communication service such as the operation of jeepneys or taxis, storage and warehousing activities, messengerial services, etc.	15	15
Mining and quarrying activities such as mineral extraction like salt making, gold mining, gravel, sand and stone quarrying, etc.	0	0
Construction like repair of house, building or any structure.	2	2

Activities not elsewhere classified, including electricity, gas and water, financing, insurance, real estate and business services	0	0
Salaries and wages from employed members	44	44
Net share of crops, fruits, and vegetables produced or livestock and poultry raised by other households	0	0
Remittances from Overseas Filipino Workers	0	0
Other Cash receipts, gifts, support, relief, and other income from abroad including pensions, retirement, workmen's compensation, dividends from investments, etc.	0	0
Cash receipts, support, assistance, relief, and other income from domestic sources, including assistance from government and private sources	6	6
Rentals received from non-agricultural lands, buildings, spaces, and other properties	0	0
Interest from bank deposits, interest from loans extended to other families.	1	1
Pension and retirement, workmen's compensation, and social security benefits	0	0
Dividends from investments	1	1
Other sources of income not elsewhere classified	9	9
Total	100	100

Table 8 shows the socio-economic profile of the respondents in terms of source of income. Most of the respondents got their income from the salaries and wages of their employed members. It gathered the highest percentage of 44%. Since they live near the coastal areas, 27% of the respondents' income came from fishing activities such as the capture of fish; gathering of fry, shells, seaweeds, etc.; and culturing fish, oysters, mussels, etc. Fifteen percent of them got their income from transportation, storage, and communication services such as the operation of jeepneys or taxis, storage and warehousing activities, messengerial services, etc. Nine percent of the respondents said that they have other sources of income not elsewhere classified. Wholesale and retail trade including market vending, sidewalk vending peddling, etc. is the source of income for 6% of the residents.

Table 9. Training Needs Assessment

Type of Program	F	%
Health Assistance	35	23.81
Supplemental Feeding	11	7.48
Educational Scholarship	30	20.41
Skills and Livelihood Training Program	71	48.30
Others	0	0
Total	147	100

Table 9 presents the training needs assessment of the different types of programs. It shows that 71% of the respondents want to have a skills and livelihood training program in their respective barangay. Thirty-five percent of the respondents want to have a health assistance program. It is due to the current pandemic that most people are in. The educational scholarship program got 30% and supplemental feeding got the lowest percentage of 11%.

Vale (2016) enumerated the importance of skills and livelihood training programs. According to Vale, the training can create sustainable livelihood opportunities for vulnerable groups particularly young women and men, through skills and entrepreneurship training in identified market linkages. It can also strengthen the community organization and self-management skills by facilitating training and workshops on leadership and value formation as well as community participation in the implementation of various livelihood community projects.

Scrutinizing Table 10 displays that the majority of the training needs assessment in terms of skills and livelihood training programs wished to have training on Automotive technology with 22%. It was followed by the training on food processing with 19.72%. The training in Basic Cookery was 14.085, training in Welding was 9.86%, and training in candle making was 7.04%. Housekeeping garnered 5.63% with 4 respondents. It was then followed by dressmaking and computer programming with 2.81%. Lastly, bread and pastry making, tailoring, basic AutoCAD, electrical, and electronics all got the lowest percentage of 1.41%.

Table 10. Training Needs Assessment in terms of the Skills and Livelihood Training Program

Type of Skills and Livelihood Training Program	F	%
Bread and Pastry Making	1	1.41
Dressmaking	2	2.81
Tailoring	1	1.41
Candle Making	5	7.04
Computer Programming	2	2.81
Housekeeping	4	5.63
Basic Cookery	10	14.08
Food Processing	14	19.72
T-Shirt Printing	0	0
Welding	7	9.86
Basic AutoCAD	1	1.41
Automotive	22	30.99
Electrical	1	1.44
Electronics	1	1.44
Others	0	0
Total	71	100

Table 11. Extent of Support of Coastal Residents

Extent of Support of Coastal Residents	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating
I will attend all meetings held by any program implemented in our village or barangay.	4.44	Extremely Support
I will join in maintaining the peace and order while a project is taking place.	4.10	Support
I will devote time and energy to carry out the activities held in the said program.	3.57	Support
I will be involved in the development of our community.	4.13	Support
I will follow and apply the good things I learn in the program.	4.13	Support
Total	4.07	Support

Table 11 implies the extent of support of the coastal residents for the programs to be launched. With an overall weighted mean of 4.07, the coastal residents of the selected

barangay in Orani, Bataan agreed to support the programs to be conducted by the institution. They agreed to attend all meetings held by any program implemented in their village or barangay with the highest mean of 4.44 interpreted as extreme support. The statement that they will devote time and energy to carry out the activities held in the said program got the lowest mean of 3.57, however, it is still interpreted as support.

Therefore, it can be said that the extent of support has many benefits. The main aim of public support is to encourage the public to have meaningful input into the decision-making process. Participation and support thus provide the opportunity for communication between agencies making decisions and the public. This communication can be an early warning system for public concerns, a means through which accurate and timely information can be disseminated, and can contribute to sustainable decision-making.

Conclusion

1. In terms of the profile of the respondents, the majority of them are 41 – 45 years old. There is an equal percentage of respondents of both male and female. The majority of the families stayed in the barangay since birth. The family has 1 to 3 members. In general, there is one (1) child per family, and at least one (1) member per family has a job. There is also one (1) member of the family ages 17 and below and no member ages 65 and above. Finally, the majority of the respondents declared that they don't have a member with disability. In terms of educational attainment, majority of the respondents were elementary graduate.
2. In terms of the socio-economic profile of the respondents, the majority of them have a monthly income of Php16,000.00 to Php19,999.00. The majority of the coastal residents have Php20,000.00 to Php24,999.00 monthly expenses. Finally, most of them got their income from the salaries and wages of their employed members.
3. In general, the respondents wanted to have a skills and livelihood training program in their respective barangay. The majority of the training needs assessment in terms of skills and livelihood training program wished to have training on automotive technology, food processing, basic cookery, Welding, and candle making respectively.
4. The study revealed that the coastal residents of the selected barangay in Orani, Bataan agreed to support the programs to be conducted by the institution.

Recommendations

1. The institution must find ways to develop and implement a viable gender-based Extension Service Program for the coastal residents.
2. The personnel or extensionists should work hand in hand in improving the service of delivery of extension services to target clientele.
3. Proper monitoring of the financial practices utilized in the project should be done periodically.

4. Intensive monitoring and assessment should be made to meet the standards set by the government with regards to extension services operation reared the welfare of its client.

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